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STRUCTURE OF THE CAUSES OF INFERTILITY IN MEN AND WOMEN IN SAMARKAND AND SAMARKAND REGION

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Annotation. *The structure of the causes of infertility was studied in 100 couples (200 people) suffering from infertility in the city of Samarkandey, Samarkand region (50 families each). It was found that in the examined women, the main place in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (diffuse goiter with subclinical hypothyroidism, ovarian failure with menstrual dysfunction, polycystic ovary syndrome, hyperandrogenism, luteal phase deficiency, impaired folliculogenesis), as well as inflammatory diseases of the genitourinary system (TORCH -infections). In the examined men, the main role in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (androgen deficiency associated with excess body weight, impaired spermatogenesis, hypergonadotropic and hypogonadotropic hypogonadism).*

Keywords: *reproductive health, infertility, male and female hypogonadism.*

СТРУКТУРА ПРИЧИН БЕСПЛОДИЯ У МУЖЧИН И ЖЕНЩИН САМАРКАНДА И САМАРКАНДСКОЙ ОБЛАСТИ

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***Аннотация.** Структура причин бесплодия изучена у 100 пар (200 человек), страдающих бесплодием в городе Самаркандей Самаркандской области (по 50 семей). Установлено, что у обследованных женщин основное место в генезе бесплодия занимают гормональные дисфункции (диффузный зоб при субклиническом гипотиреозе, овариальная недостаточность с нарушением менструальной функции, синдром поликистозных яичников, гиперандрогения, недостаточность лютеиновой фазы, нарушение фолликулогенеза), а также а также воспалительные заболевания мочеполовой системы (TORCH-инфекции). У обследованных мужчин основную роль в генезе бесплодия играют гормональные дисфункции (андрогенная недостаточность, связанная с избыточной массой тела, нарушением сперматогенеза, гипергонадотропным и гипогонадотропным гипогонадизмом).*

***Ключевые слова:** репродуктивное здоровье, бесплодие, мужской и женский гипогонадизм.*

Introduction. The problem of infertility in marriage, despite significant advances in diagnosis and treatment, remains the most pressing medical and social problem of our time [3–10]. According to WHO (1993), with an infertility rate of 15% and above, its impact on demographic indicators significantly exceeds the total impact of miscarriage and perinatal losses, and therefore this problem has not only medical and biological, but also important social significance [8, 11]. In this regard, WHO has developed a special research program on human reproduction, the main directions of which are studying the frequency and causes of infertility, standardizing the examination of infertile couples [11]. According to WHO estimates, in Uzbekistan the frequency of infertile marriages significantly exceeds the critical level and is becoming a national problem. Despite the urgency of the problem, there is no unified methodology for identifying and examining infertile couples [1, 2]. In addition, a number of medical and social aspects of this problem have not yet become the subject of scientific analysis. The problem of individual prediction of the risk of female infertility has not been solved. Despite a significant number of publications devoted to various issues of infertility, insufficient attention is paid to the prevention of this pathology [3]. According to O.N. Petrushenkova [7], the frequency of infertility at a large industrial enterprise involved in the automotive industry was 15.1%, which exceeds the critical level determined by WHO experts (15%), at which infertile marriage represents a national problem due to its significant impact on demographic indicators. The prevalence of primary female

infertility was 4.5%, secondary - 10.6% [7]. It has been shown that infertility in marriage is caused by impaired reproductive function of women in 83.1% of cases. In 16.9% of married couples suffering from infertility, reproductive dysfunction was diagnosed in both spouses. The structure of the causes of female infertility is dominated by: tubal-peritoneal factor (38.5%), endocrine infertility (27.7%), genital endometriosis (23.0%). In 50.8% of women, infertility is caused by a combination of 2–4 factors. The most common causes of male infertility are: idiopathic oligozoospermia (36.3%), genital infection (27.3%) and varicocele (18.2%).

Purpose of the study— to study the structure of the causes of infertility in men and women in the city of Samarkand and the Samarkand region according to screening data.

Material and research methods. From October 2020 to June 2023, we conducted sociological and medical studies in a comparative aspect among families from rural and urban areas in the context of individual territories representing the corresponding regions of the country, in order to determine the causes of infertility (endocrine, non-endocrine, etc.) in spouses and selection of further management tactics and possible treatment (Samarkand and Samarkand region: Nurabad, Urgut and Pastdargom districts). A total of 100 married couples were examined - 200 people (100 men and 100 women of fertile age). The study material included men and women of reproductive age who are in infertile marriages and undergoing treatment for infertility or are registered in regional endocrinological dispensaries. The sample size is 200 people (100 men and 100 women), or 100 families. The study covered families in the city of Samarkand and the Samarkand region - 50 families each (Nurabad, Urgut and Pastdargom districts). Also, 50 individuals were examined using the Beck Anxiety Inventory (25 men and 25 women). The following methods were used during the study: the first stage - focus group, conversation, questionnaire for identifying depression and anxiety (Beck); as well as specially developed questionnaires for this medical study, etc.; the second stage is sampling. All study participants were divided into four groups. The first group is women suffering from infertility, aged 18 to 35 years. The second group is men suffering from infertility, aged 25 to 40 years. The third group is parents whose child (male or female) suffers from infertility. The fourth group is representatives of social institutions of the local community: leaders and activists of the mahalla committee, leaders and members of the mahalla women's council, doctors of the local medical institution. In mixed groups (third and fourth), the distribution of participants by gender was also taken

into account, i.e. the marginal ratio was 7:3. A total of 8 focus groups were conducted, with a focus group including 20 people. Sociological questionnaires have been developed for focus groups - separately for the husband, for the wife, and for the mother-in-law. During the study, 50 people (25 couples) out of 200 participants underwent psychological testing (Beck Anxiety and Depression Inventory). The answer in the first column is 0 points, the answer in the second column (slightly) is 1 point, the answer in the third column (moderate) is 2 points, the answer in the fourth column is 3 points. Then all points are summed up. The total score is interpreted as follows: 0–5 points—normal anxiety, 6–8—mild anxiety, 9–18—moderate anxiety, above 19—high anxiety. At the third stage, if necessary, patients were sent for further examination: CT/MRI of the pituitary gland, ultrasound of the genital organs, hormonal studies (LH, FSH, estradiol, progesterone, testosterone, TSH, prolactin), folliculometry (FM), spermogram, etc. FM was performed vaginally with ultrasound method starting from the 7th–8th day of the menstrual cycle (MC). For completeness of information, FM data were compared with BT and hormonal parameters.

Research results and discussion. The frequency of complaints of respondents on the Beck anxiety scale for the city of Samarkand and the Samarkand region is presented. According to the results of the analysis of the Beck scale, as can be seen from the table. 1, residents of Tashkent and the Samarkand region are not significantly susceptible to depression and anxiety in relation to infertility. Of the 200 men and women examined in Samarkand and the Samarkand region, 40 women and 40 men were examined, married from one to five years and suffering from primary or secondary infertility. In table. Figure 2 shows the structure of the causes of infertility in examined women aged 25 to 35 years suffering from infertility in Samarkand and the Samarkand region. As can be seen, in the examined women, the main place in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (diffuse goiter with subclinical hypothyroidism, ovarian failure with menstrual dysfunction, polycystic ovary syndrome, hyperandrogenism, luteal phase deficiency, impaired folliculogenesis), as well as inflammatory diseases of the genitourinary system (TORCH - infections). The structure of the causes of infertility in examined men aged 25 to 40 years suffering from infertility in Samarkand and the Samarkand region is given. In the examined men from the city and village, the main place in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (androgen deficiency associated with excess body weight, impaired spermatogenesis, hypergonadotropic and hypogonadotropic hypogonadism). Thus, in men with

infertility, significantly low values of average values of LH, FSH, free and total testosterone (hypogonadotropic hypogonadism) were found against the background of normoprolactinemia. Women were characterized by significantly low levels of LH, FSH, estradiol, progesterone on the 14th day of MC against the background of hyperprolactinemia, that is, anovulatory cycles. Infertility does not have a direct negative impact on the process of socialization of people with this diagnosis in the family, in the local community and at work [12]. This revealed fact indicates a deep transformation of values taking place in society. According to the modern understanding of the hierarchy of values, a person in himself is the highest value, without taking into account whether he is capable or incapable of childbearing. The reproductive function of a person is important, one might say the most important, for a person and for society, but it is not decisive, primary and decisive in determining the meaning of a person's life [13, 14]. Thus, for the normal and full socialization of a person diagnosed with infertility into public, social institutions, there are no objective or subjective obstacles. The socialization of people diagnosed with infertility depends critically on family members, and primarily on the husband or wife and their parents [16, 17].

Conclusions

1. According to the results of the Beck scale, residents of Tashkentai and the Samarkand region are not significantly susceptible to depression and anxiety regarding infertility.

2. In the examined women, the main place in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction, as well as inflammatory diseases of the genitourinary system.

3. In the examined men, the main role in the genesis of infertility is occupied by hormonal dysfunction (androgen deficiency associated with excess body weight, impaired spermatogenesis, hypergonadotropic and hypogonadotropic hypogonadism). 4. In men with infertility, significantly low values of average values of LH, FSH, free and total testosterone (hypogonadotropic hypogonadism) were found against the background of normoprolactinemia. Women were characterized by significantly low levels of LH, FSH, estradiol, progesterone on the 14th day of the menstrual cycle against the background of hyperprolactinemia (anovulatory cycles).

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